

ISic3405

epitaph of Truphon

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

terracotta

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015-01-13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Santa Croce di Camarina

Provenance

catacomb, Santa Croce di Camarina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 36 cm

Width 36 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. τάφος Τρύφων

2. ος πρυσβυτέρου

3. #

Apparatus

Text after NSA

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644950

PHI 140557

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0255b (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 382
Pace, B. 1927. Camarina: topografia, storia, archeologia. Catania. At 163 no.31

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3405. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358492>